

Summary Table

Model	Training Bal. Acc.	Testing Bal. Acc.	Sign Test (p)	CV Consistency
[a]	0.5436	0.5289	7 (0.1719)	9/10
[b a]	0.5579	0.5286	10 (0.0010)	8/10
[c b a]	0.5870	0.5346	10 (0.0010)	5/10
[c d a e]	0.6174	0.5290	8 (0.0547)	7/10
[c d b a e]	0.6620	0.5301	8 (0.0547)	10/10
[c f d b a e]	0.6777	0.5237	6 (0.3770)	10/10

HABP2rs7923349, ITGA2rs4865756, IL1Ars1609682, ITGA2rs1991013, HABP2rs932650 and IL1Ars1800587 are symbolized as a-f, respectively.